

Sensory Analysis on Readymade Neem Beverage

Ethnographic Study with One-on-One Interviews, Focus Group Discussions, and
Conjoint Analysis

(Application of Conjoint Analysis at the Fuzzy Front End in Product Development)

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Executed By:

Simon Bediako Addo & Audery Ameley Armah

Report Prepared By:

Cecille Wendy Aboagye

Reviewed By:

Dr. Maame Yaakwaah Blay Adjei

Funding Acquisition By:

Dorcas Osei-Safo

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Summary

SUMMARY

This report presents a sensory and consumer research study investigating perceptions, usage patterns, and sensory expectations for neem-based beverages in Ghana. Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) is widely consumed in various traditional forms, particularly for its perceived medicinal benefits. This research applied a mixed-methods approach—ethnographic interviews, focus group discussions, and conjoint analysis—to understand how consumers use neem, what sensory attributes they associate with quality and effectiveness, and which attributes influence product acceptance.

Findings indicate that neem's bitterness is culturally linked to medicinal efficacy, yet excessive bitterness limits acceptability for wider beverage applications. Honey and selected fruits (e.g., pineapple, lemon) were strongly preferred as bitterness-mitigating ingredients. Conjoint analysis confirmed that the most desirable neem beverage characteristics include moderated bitterness, absence of lingering aftertaste, a light green product colour, and honey as a flavouring component. These insights provide an evidence-based foundation for future research, formulation studies, and sensory validation efforts involving neem beverages.

Introduction

New Product Development is essential for driving growth, innovation, and competitiveness in the food industry (Drechsler et al., 2013). It is typically a multi-phase process that progresses from idea generation to product design, optimization, and eventually, commercialization (Phaisuwat et al., 2017). The early ideation stage often referred to as the “fuzzy front end” is characterized by uncertainty, limited structure, and evolving concepts; yet it plays a critical role in determining the success of new products. During this phase, a clear understanding of consumer needs, expectations, and preferences is vital (Reid & De Brentani, 2004).

Consumer insights form the foundation of successful food product development, especially at the ideation stage. They help identify the sensory attributes, functionalities, and benefits that consumers value in a potential product. For a neem tea beverage, such insights are crucial for understanding what consumers expect in terms of appearance, flavour, aroma, and overall acceptability. To generate these insights, a consumer-led approach is often recommended. Qualitative methods such as interviews and focus group discussions (McDonagh-Philp & Bruseberg, 2000; Kärkkäinen, et al., 2001) allow researchers to explore consumer perceptions, motivations, and usage experiences in depth. These methods help uncover emerging trends and attitudes, especially for products rooted in traditional or medicinal value. Complementing these, conjoint analysis offers a quantitative way of determining the relative importance of product attributes and identifying combinations that maximize consumer preference (Chung et al., 2011).

In Ghana, the use of neem leaves increased substantially during the COVID-19 pandemic due to their perceived medicinal benefits. This heightened interest

sparked the exploration of a neem-based beverage as a functional product. In response, the present study employed a qualitative approach to identify attributes relevant to consumers of neem extracts. Subsequently, insights from interviews and focus groups were integrated with conjoint analysis to evaluate the importance of these attributes in a hypothetical neem tea beverage. The findings provide an evidence-based guide for developing a consumer-oriented neem beverage with improved chances of market acceptance.

Objective:

To identify neem users and explore their usage patterns and reasons for using neem

Specific objectives:

- Determine common uses of neem by consumers
- Determine consumers' willing to consume neem leaf as a tea
- Determine the usage and consumption preferences of consumers for a neem leaf tea beverage concept.

3. Methodology

Ethnographic study using observations with one-on-one interviews, focus group discussion and conjoint analysis were used to determine how consumers want to consume a neem tea beverage.

Ethnographic study with one-on-one interview

Observations

Four locations were selected for the test, three urban areas and one rural area. They included:

- Lashibi in the Tema West constituency
- Wiaboman in the Weija constituency
- Ogbodjo in the Adentan Constituency
- Tsofoli in the Ningo prampram constituency (Rural area).

In these locations, school parks, community grounds and other public spaces where neem trees could be sighted were observed. The general physical landscape of selected locations were considered, and pictures taken. Pictures were also taken in homes of participants where neem beverage had been prepared.

One-on-one interviews

A total of 42 Neem tree users were approached and interviewed using an interview guide. Probing was done when answers given were not clear. Selection of consumers was done via convenient sampling. Some specific questions asked were on: Parts of neem used, Neem usage and storage, patronage of neem as a ready-made beverage and how readymade neem beverage can be made more appealing

Data analysis

Thematic analysis was used to identify and develop relevant themes

Focus group discussion

Three focus group discussions were conducted to find out what participants thought about some readymade neem tea products and their suggestions to improve them. The discussions lasted between 80 - 100 minutes. Two of the discussions were conducted in the sensory evaluation laboratory and the third at Ogbojo. Discussions held in the lab were done in English and in Ogbojo, it was done in Twi. A total of 21 people participated in the discussions. Participants gave their consent for voice recording and pictures to be taken. The discussion was centered on these main themes:

1. Current level of knowledge, and usage of neem
2. Understanding how the issue about bitterness in neem can be improved.
3. Acceptance of some neem tea prototypes
4. Purchase intent

Probing was done to clarify points made by participants. All views were allowed to be expressed freely without recourse to the investigators. Each participant received an incentive at the end of the session.

The global theme underlying this discussion was to understand how the issue about bitterness in neem could be improved and determine the level of acceptance of some neem tea prototypes. For the latter part, an sensory tasting activity was conducted as a way to get more insights. Dried neem leaves were prepared into tea and served to participants to give their views. One gram of the leaves was steeped in 500ml of boiling water for 10mins and served to assessors warm and cold.

Figure 1: Dried Neem leaves

Figure 2: 100% Neem Beverage

After tasting, assessors were given the opportunity to suggest ingredients that can be added to improve the flavour. The ingredients they came up with included sugar, honey, cinnamon, milk, powdered ginger and pineapple essence.

The next activity involved presenting tea prototypes. The prototypes were prepared by steeping one tea bag in 500ml boiling water for 10 minutes.

Data analysis

Thematic analysis was used to identify and develop relevant themes

Conjoint analysis

Thirty adults aged 18 years and above participated in the study. The test was primarily administered online; however, some participants visited the laboratory to complete the same online module under supervision. All participants provided informed consent prior to participation.

Seven factors were identified from the focus group discussions and interviews. Five factors had three levels each, while the remaining two had two levels and five levels, respectively. XLSTAT was used to produce 16 unique product profiles representing combinations of these attribute levels. Each profile was presented in both verbal and

pictorial formats to enhance comprehension. Participants completed a ranking-based conjoint task in Compusense (Compusense Inc., Guelph, Ontario, Canada). Each participant viewed all 16 product profiles and ranked them from most preferred (1) to least preferred (16). The factors and levels obtained are Table 1.

Table 1: Factors considered in creating the neem tea beverage combinations

Form	Authentication	Added ingredients (AIng)	Colour	Aroma	Bitterness	Aftertaste
A ready to drink liquid	Made from fresh leaves	AIng1	Light green colour	No smell	Not bitter	Lingering bitterness
Leaves dried and packaged as a tea bag	Made from dehydrated leaves	AIng2	Moderate green colour	Smells like neem	Perceptible bitterness	Added ingredients lingering
Leaves dried and broken for self brewing		AIng3	Deep green colour	Smells like added ingredients	Very bitter	No lingering aftertaste
		AIng4				
		Only neem				

AIng = Added Ingredient. These have been anonymized for confidentiality reasons

Results

Observations

Generally, neem trees were found to grow around public spaces in a scattered form. They usually were found around school buildings or were used as shade trees. In homes, neem leaves were found to be steeped in alcohol (commonly akpeteshie- a local gin) to develop bitters. Mostly the neem leaves are dried prior to being steeped in alcohol. The pictures below show how neem as identified in public spaces as well as in homes.

Figure 3: Neem trees found in the communities

Figure 4: Boiled leaves in a saucepan

Figure 5: Boiled leaves ready to be discarded

Figure 6: Neem leaves steeped in Akpeteshie for bitters

Figure 7: Presenting participants with incentive after interview

ETHNOGRAPHIC RESULTS

Figure 8: Gender of respondents

A total of 42 respondents were interviewed. 22 of them were females and 20 were males.

Figure 9: Age range of respondents

Respondents from all age ranges were interviewed. Those within the age range of 45 to 54 were more followed by 35 to 44 and 55 to 64 then 25 to 34. From the results we could say those who consume the neem beverage are generally from 25 years and above. During recruitment it was difficult getting children within 12 to 17. Most of them complained of the bitterness of neem hence, their refusal to consume it.

Figure 10: Ethnicity of respondents

Respondents interviewed belonged to the various ethnic groups in Ghana except Guan. Most of them were Ga/Adangbe because the rural area visited was a an Adangbe community.

Figure 11: Ethnicity of respondents

Majority of the respondents had received some form of education. Only two people mentioned that they had never been to school. A few were reluctant to mention their educational level. Some felt offended when asked of the educational level.

One-on-one interview

Five main sub-organising themes were discernible under this domain. They include: parts of the neem used, Uses of the neem, Storage of the processed neem beverage, patronizing readymade neem beverage and making readymade neem beverage more appealing.

Part of the neem used

All the parts of the neem tree were used. The parts include the leaves, seeds, bark, branch/twigs, roots, and flowers. The most used parts were the leaves [N=42]

"The ones growing at the tip of the branch".

The leaves, he young part of the leaves you harvest".

"The one that grows freshly".

Which was followed by the branches or twigs [N=12].

"The twigs are used for chewing".

"If you are not sick you can chew it off and as a chewing stick".

"Yes I use the branches as chewing stick".

The leaves were prepared in various ways. Some of which include boiling with other ingredients [N=10],

"I boil it, add hwentia (negro pepper) and drink it".

"I boiled the leaves with lime and took it like that".

"We boil it together with lemon then drink". When boiling, to enhance the fragrance, I sometimes chop lemon to add and to reduce the bitterness, i chop pineapple in it".

OR boiling alone[N=22],

"I boil the leaves and drink the resulting mixture".

"I boiled it on fire with water".

"I cook the leaves and drink".

macerating alone [N=15],

" Macerate and sieve it then drink it".

"I sometime macerate and drink it".

"The herbs you will macerate it and it will be smooth. The water would become green, then you will sieve it. Then it will become like water then you add salt and then you drink it".

Or macerating with other ingredients [N=5]

"You mash it, seive it and add salt then you drink it".

" We also blend the leaves and add salt when we are tired".

"I got a fever, so I pussa it, added a lime and drank it".

and steeping or blending in alcohol [N=2].

"Sometimes I blend the fresh leaves with Akpeteshie then sieve it into the main bottle for sale".

"I put the leaves into a bucket and pour the drink on it and allow it to stay for three days".

The branches were just chewed [N=11].

"Some chew the branches to brush the teeth".

"Yes, we use the branch too, we break the branch/stick and chew".

"Yes, the twigs, we sometimes chew it".

Uses of the neem leaves

The leaves were used in different ways. Some drunk it [N=42],

" I sometimes rub it and drink the liquid".

"During December 2021, I boiled the leaves and drunk it as cure for malaria".

" I boil it, drink the water and sometimes bath it or puu it."

Others used it to bath [N=8]

"I have used it to bath before".

"I used it to bath".

"After puuing, I used it to bath".

And others "puu" (steam inhale) it [N=27].

" I can aslo puu".

"When I mush and sieve the leaves, I cook it and put it in a bucket. When I got to the bathroom, then I use a cloth and cover myself".

"I use it for puuing".

Consumers used neem leaves because they believed it mainly cured fever [N=24]

"It is able to stop fever".

" I used it to cure fever".

"It has been long because I used it when the fever was present".

Malaria [N=18].

"The leaves because it is medicinal and can treat malaria".

"Anytime I feel I have malaria".

"No, I use it for only malaria".

Some people also said they were able to sleep well when they drunk neem leave beverage [N=2],

"Personally, it helps me sleep well when I take it in the evening".

"When I drink it in the evening, I feel very dizzy and sleepy and helps me sleep".

and it relieved stomach and body pains [N=3].

"To cure malaria and stomach pains".

"Like I said, I boiled it with lime when I feel pains and fever symptoms".

"Yes, when I see that I am getting chilly and start getting back aches, then I plug it".

They were able to detect its effectiveness because it causes them

to sweat a lot [N=8]. They believe the sickness leaves the body through sweating.

"When you drink it, you sweat a lot".

"When you have fever, and you take it you start to sweat, and you see the difference".

"When you drink it, you begin to sweat. You will keep sweating. It is through the sweating that the sickness leaves the body".

Their urine colour changed [N=5]. The colour changed meant the sickness was moving from the body into the urine.

"When I drink it, I feel better, and my urine colour also changes".

"You keep urinating, and the urine is yellow".

"After consuming I urinated yellow continuously, and yes I saw it worked".

And they generally felt much better than before [N=42]. It was very effective in curing them.

"The next morning, after I wake up, I feel very free".

"Yes, it really solves my problem".

"Because I have experienced it severally. I feel better when I take it. I don't need to take any malaria drug. I started taking this around 2017-2018."

The beverage can be drunk in the morning [N=24], afternoon [N=8], or evening [N=26]. Most people consumed the beverage twice a day. Others consumed it three times a day and some also consumed it only once a day.

"Morning, afternoon and evening".

"During that time, I took it morning, afternoon and evening".

"Morning, afternoon and evening".

Storage

Some people prepared it in bulk [20]. Those who prepared it in bulk either stored it in the fridge or rewarmed it every day until the content was finished or the bitterness was lost.

"We keep drinking and refilling with fresh water. We stop refilling when it has lost its bitterness".

"Especially in the evening, when you heat it and drink it, doesn't go bad because if you put it down without boiling it, it will go bad".

" I put it in the refrigerator".

Others prepared it and consumed all in a day or at once [N=7]. Those who consumed all in a day were those who usually macerated and drunk the liquid produced.

"I don't make it in excess, I make what I can take in a day".

"I made enough for myself and the family so there is no excess".

"I make just a small amount that I can consume all".

Patronizing a readymade neem product

When asked if they would patronize a readymade neem product most people liked the idea [N=36]. They liked the idea because of how effective neem leaves are.

"Yes, because neem is very effective".

"I will buy it because I know how effective it is".

"Yes, if you bring, I will buy."

Those who said no [N=4] explained that they wouldn't be able to ensure the leaves used were fresh. One person said there was no way she was going to patronize it because of its bitterness.

"No. it is supposed to be in its fresh state. It's not good to be dried. I haven't seen anyone use the dry one before".

"No because it is very bitter. I don't want to drink it again".

" No because I wouldn't be able to tell if the leaves used in making it are fresh".

For a readymade product most people suggested that it should be in a liquid form because that is the form they are used to [N=28].

"I would prefer it boiled and bottled like a local drink, like the sobolo bottled drink".

"I like the leaves, in a liquid form like how herbal drugs are, like the ones in the pharmacy, because I think it will be very effective in curing malaria".

"Drink form".

A few said it could be in a tea bag which can be dropped in a cup of hot water and consumed at any time [N=9].

"If it can be bagged in a tea bag or the dried leaves are sold".

"In the form of tea leaves or a liquid form".

" I will be okay with a tea bag. Put it in hot water and just drink".

Or powdered form [N=4].

"If you do it as powder it is fine".

" I would prefer it in a powdered form".

" When you make it into a powdered product it would be better".

Making readymade neem beverage more appealing.

For the bitterness some wanted it to be maintained because they believed medicine must be bitter to remain effective [N=7].

"No, it means you don't want to get well quickly. Bitter medicine cures you faster".

"No, its fine. The bitterness is fine. We are made to understand that if the thing is sweet, they are not effective".

"It should be left as it is because if the bitterness is reduced, I don't think it will be effective".

"No, I don't, but my brother adds pineapple to his. I think when you add something to it, it reduces its efficacy, because, when we all drink ours, we feel better faster than he does. He takes longer to recover compared to us".

While others preferred it less bitter [N=9].

"Do you mean they would add sugar. If it's something like pineapple that would really help me because the bitterness would be reduced".

"O that one I will drink"

It was suggested that ingredients such as pineapple, lemon/lime and sugarcane could be added to improve on the flavour and smell [N=6].

"I know some people add pineapple and sugar cane. They all help reduce fever, but I prefer to take it without adding anything".

"Some people even add pineapple leaves".

"I think you can add lemon and pineapple to it to mask the bitter and unpleasant flavor of the neem drink".

To find out if the product would sell, the participants were asked what will make them reach out for a neem beverage. Most of them said they would buy it once they know it's a neem product because they already know the effectiveness of neem [N=20].

"A lot of people are sick in Ghana oo. They will buy".

" I know what neem can do so I will purchase it".

" Because it is a medicine that cures diseases, so I will buy it".

Some also said they would always go in for it if they saw how effective it was after the first try [N=9].

"If I take it and its good, I will buy it".

" I have the opportunity to see and taste one then I will buy".

"If I use it and it works, I will keep buying it".

One person said the price would determine whether to purchase it or not [N=1].

"Yes, provided the price is reasonable".

Conclusion for one-on-one interview

The leaves of the neem are generally used for medicinal purposes. Some users don't mind the bitterness, but others would rather prefer something is done to reduce its bitterness. Most people would embrace a readymade neem beverage but would patronize it if it's as effective as the ones they prepare on their own and if its affordable. They would generally prefer the readymade product in a liquid form since that is the form they are used to.

Focus group discussion

Demographics

Table 2; Gender of participants

Group	Males	Females
Grp1	2	3
Grp2	5	4
Grp3	6	1

Table 3: Age range of participants

Age/groups	Grp1	Grp2	Grp3
18-24	2	7	3
25-34	0	2	0
35-44	1	0	1
45-54	2	0	0
65-64	0	0	3

Grp 1 had more females than males and most participants belonged to the age group 18-24 and 45-54. Grp 2 had more males than females and majority of the participants were between the ages of 18-24. Grp 3 also had more males with only one female. Majority of the participants in Grp 3 were between the age ranges of 18-24 and 55-64.

Table 4: Occupation of participants

Occupation	Grp 1	Grp2	Grp3
Student	2	6	2
Unemployed	0	0	1
National service personnel	0	2	0
Skilled labour (hairdressers, carpenters etc)	0	0	4
Office and Administrative support occupation	2	1	0
Art, design, entertainment, sports and media occupation	1	0	0

Table 5: Gross monthly salary

Gross monthly salary	Grp 1	Grp 2	Grp 3
<GHS 500	2	5	2
GHS 501-1000	0	3	3
GHS 1001 - 3500	2	1	2
GHS 6,501-10,000	1	0	0

Grp 1 participants were students and administrative workers generally earning less than GHS500 -10,000. Most participants in Grp 2 were students, generally earning less than GHS 500. Those in Grp 3 were mostly skilled workers with most participants earning between GHS 500- 1000.

Tea consumption pattern of participants

Figure 12: Purpose for drinking tea

Figure 13: Consumption frequency of tea by participants

All participants had consumed tea before. Most participants in Grp 2 drunk tea everyday and those in Grp 1 and 3 mostly consumed tea at least once a week.

Generally, most of the participants consumed tea as a source of food and for health benefits.

Five main sub-organising themes were also obtained for the focus group. They include: current level of knowledge and usage, issues of bitterness in 100% neem, improving the sensory properties of 100% neem beverage, selecting the most liked prototype and factors influencing confidence of authenticity.

Current level of knowledge and usage

All participants from Grp3 had consumed neem beverage before. A few participants in Grp 1 and 2 had never consumed neem before. For neem tea bag only two people in Grp 1 mentioned they had heard of it before. Forms they suggested neem can be processed into include a tea bag, broken leaves stored in a container and a drink.

Issue of bitterness in 100% neem

All groups admitted that neem was generally bitter. All groups mentioned that the bitterness in the product presented was not intense and the colour was lighter than what they were used to. Most participants liked the light green colour. One person in Grp 1 preferred a darker product. Someone in Grp 1 also admitted that the products were very similar to the locally made one. In all three groups some participants said the bitterness in the cold tea lingered longer. Overall, most people liked the low

bitter intensity of the tea. One participant in Grp 1 said his children would be able to drink the tea since it was not as bitter as the one he boils at home.

Improving the sensory properties of 100% neem beverage

Suggested ingredients include: sugar-Grp1,2 & 3, honey- Grp1,2 & 3, lemon-Grp 1, cinnamon-Grp 2, milk- Grp 1, mint-Grp 1 & 2, sweet fruit-Grp 2, ginger-Grp 1 & 2 and essence-Grp 2 & 3.

"If they add pineapple or ginger, the ginger especially"

They were provided with: sugar, honey, cinnamon, milk, powdered ginger and pineapple essence.

The most liked ingredient was honey for all groups.

" Me the honey reduced the bitterness"

"Cos for honey, it has a natural flavour and has benefits, but with the sugar, no not at all"

Selecting the most liked prototype

The most liked was the lemon mint combination. The second liked was the pineapple mint combination. Some didn't like the negro pepper because it gave the product a more herbal taste. Some complained that the mango flavour could not be perceived. They were disappointed when they didn't feel the pungency of ginger in mango

ginger combination. They perceived more of the lemon than the neem in lemon neem combination. They mentioned that the lemon was overpowering.

"I think the lemon was more like I could smell it more"

Participants were also asked if they would like the prototypes as a drink or tea bag.

Those who wanted it as a drink said it was more convenient and handy. For those who selected the tea bag, they said they would like to prepare it themselves.

"I want to prepare it myself"

Factors influencing confidence of authenticity

All groups didn't mind drinking the prototypes as a beverage. Some participants in Grp1 were ready to purchase it as soon as it gets on the market. Generally, all they wanted was to be sure its efficacy as medicine was not lost.

"Honestly, I can't wait to have this on the market"

Conclusion of focus group discussion

- A lot of the participants preferred the beverage when the bitterness was reduced.
- The most preferred ingredient added was honey
- They could drink the neem tea prototypes as a beverage

Conjoint analysis

Demographics

Table 6: Age range of participants

Age range	Number of participants
18-24	14
25-34	7
35-44	4
45-54	2
55-64	3

Table 7: Educational level

Educational level	Number of participants
Undergraduate degree	19
Post graduate	11

All age groups were represented except for 65+ years. Majority of participants were between the ages of 18-24 years. All participants had received some form of undergraduate education.

Consumption of tea

Figure 14: Most participants who took part in the test like tea

There were both positive (+) and negative (-) effect of the experimented factors from the conjoint analysis. Only 9 out of the 22 were positive. They include:

1. Bitterness – not bitter
2. Added ingredients – AIng1
3. Aftertaste - no lingering aftertaste
4. Aroma - no smell
5. Aftertaste - added ingredients lingering
6. Colour - Light green colour
7. Bitterness - perceptible bitterness

8. Authentication - made from fresh leaves

9. Form - leaves dried and broken for self-brewing

Average importance

Figure 15: Average importance

The figure shows the importance of the factors. Only factors above 15% were considered. These include aftertaste, bitterness and added ingredients. This means that not all the positive factors are of importance. Factors that are both important and positive are:

1. Bitterness – not bitter
2. Bitterness - perceptible bitterness

3. Added ingredients – AIng1
4. Aftertaste - no lingering aftertaste
5. Aftertaste - added ingredients lingering

Conclusion of conjoint

So, for a neem tea beverage, consumers would want it to contain at least one added ingredient (specifically Aing1, have perceptible bitterness or no bitterness and no lingering bitter aftertaste. However, they won't mind the aftertaste of the added ingredient.

OVERALL CONCLUSION

- Neem was generally consumed for its medicinal purposes
- It is naturally bitter, but some consumers add ingredients to mask the bitterness
- When other ingredients were added to mask the bitterness, consumers were able to drink it as a beverage
- The most accepted ingredient to mask the bitterness was honey.
- Consumers were very particular about bitterness hence two of the most important factors were bitterness in the taste and aftertaste.

They preferred a beverage that was not bitter or the bitterness be perceptible with no aftertaste. The acceptable aftertaste was that of the added ingredient

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